

1 Impregnation of activated carbon with ionic liquids for simultaneous
2 removal of micropollutants and antibiotic-resistant bacteria from
3 wastewater

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Abstract

Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), often resulting from the misuse of antibiotics, have emerged as significant environmental pollutants. Their presence in wastewater poses challenges for conventional treatment methods, which fail to eliminate ARGs completely. This study investigates the use of ionic liquids (ILs) impregnated onto granular activated carbon (GAC) to enhance the removal of ARGs. Two ILs, TEDA ((N,N,N-triethyl-1-dodecylammonium bis(trifluoromethyl-sulfonyl)imide) and TEGO Dispers 662 C (commercial IL; 1-alkyl-3-methyl imidazolium methylsulphate), were used for impregnation and tested against bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Aeromonas sp.*, as well as bacteria present in real water samples from wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and greywater. The IL-impregnated GAC demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity, particularly against ARG strains A3 and A4, with >99% bacterial elimination. Notably, the adsorption capacity of GAC for most pharmaceuticals was not significantly reduced by impregnation with TEDA. Analytical and ecotoxicological tests (using *Vibrio fischeri*, *Sinapis alba*, and *Eisenia andrei*) confirmed that the ILs remained strongly bound to the GAC surface, reducing their environmental risk. The findings highlight the potential of IL-impregnated activated carbon as a selective antimicrobial agent for wastewater treatment, especially in addressing the spread of antibiotic resistance genes.

Keywords: *antibiotic resistance genes; wastewater treatment; ionic liquids; impregnated activated carbon; bacterial elimination*

44 **Introduction**

45 Despite the benefits of antibiotics, the widespread use of antibiotics has led to the emergence
46 of resistant bacteria [1,2] and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) as parts of the bacteria that
47 may have mutated due to the improper use of antibiotics. As a result, ARGs have become a new
48 type of pollutant with a high risk to the environment and humanity. The sources of antibiotics
49 in the environment can be divided into three branches – human medicine, veterinary medicine,
50 and agriculture.[3–6] From all these sources, antibiotic resistance genes enter the wastewater
51 and subsequently wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), where they are transferred further into
52 the environment as part of the effluent or in the sewage sludge. Wastewater treatment plants
53 should therefore pay more attention to the removal of these bacteria.[7,8]

54 Conventional wastewater treatment removes most bacteria, but a considerable portion of
55 antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) remains in the effluent [1,2]. Advanced disinfection
56 technologies are therefore applied, with UV irradiation followed by chlorination being the most
57 effective; the efficiency of chlorination alone can be reduced by ammoniacal nitrogen.
58 Ozonation, commonly used for hospital wastewater, is generally less effective. Further
59 reduction of microbes and ARGs can be achieved by combining ozonation with filtration
60 (activated carbon or slow sand), as demonstrated by Lüddecke et al. (2015) [9]. Sludge
61 stabilization processes such as anaerobic digestion and (vermi)composting can also reduce
62 microbial loads [10]. Ionic liquids represent a promising emerging option due to their strong
63 antimicrobial activity and their ability to remove selected ARGs [1,7,11], with potential
64 applications in eliminating antibiotic-resistant bacteria (ARB), disinfectant detergents,
65 antiseptics, or dressing additives [1,12,13].

66 Ionic liquids (ILs) are liquid salts with melting points below water and negligible vapor
67 pressure, making them non-volatile. Their use in green chemistry has expanded due to
68 recyclability, non-flammability, high polarity, electrical conductivity and thermal stability, as
69 well as their ability to dissolve a wide range of organic, inorganic and biological materials.
70 Their properties can be tailored by combining different cations and anions [14–16]]. ILs have
71 been applied in areas such as nanocomposites[14], catalysis [15–17], biomolecules [18] and gas
72 capture [19]. Many ionic liquids also exhibit antimicrobial activity [7,20,21]Fojtášková et al.
73 (2020) [22] synthesized several ionic liquids and their precursors and evaluated their properties.
74 Michalski, Sommer et al. (2023) [23] investigated antimicrobial and antiviral effects of
75 morpholinium-based herbicidal ILs. Yagci et al. (2011) [24] prepared antimicrobial

76 polyurethane films modified with ionic liquids, and Słubik et al. (2023) [25] synthesized an
77 antimicrobial IL based on a biguanide cation with thiocyanate or benzoate anions.

78 The ecotoxicity of ionic liquids varies widely, from low to very high toxicity [26]. Because
79 of the vast number of possible cation–anion combinations, conventional ecotoxicity testing is
80 difficult and costly [27]. Computational toxicology based on functional groups is therefore
81 often used to relate chemical structure to biological effects and predict IL toxicity across species
82 [28,29]. One approach to reducing their environmental impact while retaining antimicrobial
83 activity is immobilizing ILs onto suitable substrates.

84 Although ionic liquid-impregnated materials have been widely investigated for gas capture
85 and pharmaceutical adsorption, their use as selective antimicrobial agents targeting antibiotic
86 resistance genes (ARGs) in wastewater remains largely unexplored. ILs have been immobilized
87 on various substrates, such as chitosan [30], date pits [31] and mesoporous silica [32], and
88 activated carbon is also frequently functionalized. Previous studies focused mainly on gas
89 adsorption, including SO₂ [33], CO₂ [34,35], H₂S [36], H₂ [37,38], or on pharmaceutical and
90 phenol removal [39,40].

91 However, no systematic study has evaluated the ability of IL-impregnated activated carbon
92 to selectively remove ARGs from wastewater. This work therefore provides the first combined
93 assessment of IL-modified activated carbon, its antimicrobial activity against ARG-bearing
94 bacteria, and its potential ecotoxicity—introducing an innovative application that extends
95 beyond previous gas- or pharmaceutical-oriented research.

96 The aim of this work was to impregnate granular activated carbon with two types of
97 ionic liquids – the commercially available TEGO and the laboratory-synthesized TEDA (N,N,N
98 -triethyl-1-dodecylammonium bis(trifluoromethyl-sulfonyl)imide). The next steps involved
99 testing the materials' ability to suppress ARG-bearing wastewater bacteria, confirming that their
100 pharmaceutical adsorption capacity was preserved, and examining any associated ecotoxic
101 effects. Since the application of ionic liquid-impregnated activated carbon for ARGs has not
102 been systematically studied, this research addresses a relevant gap in current knowledge.

103

104 2 Material and Methods

105 2.1 Ionic liquids

106
107 Two ionic liquids (ILs) were used for the impregnation of granular activated carbon (GAC):
108 TEGO® Dispers 662C (Evonik, Germany), based on a 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium cation and
109 methylsulfate anion, and TEDA (N,N,N-triethyl-1-dodecylammonium
110 bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide). TEGO was selected as a representative of cost-effective
111 ILs, while TEDA represents quaternary ammonium ILs (QAILs) known for their biocidal
112 properties. TEDA was synthesized in two steps: (1) quaternization of triethylamine with 1-
113 bromododecane, and (2) bromide anion exchange with the lithium salt of
114 bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide, following the procedure described in [22,41].

115 2.2 Impregnation of activated carbon (AC)

116
117 Commercial GAC Hydriffin 30 N (Donau Carbon, Germany; 8 × 30 mesh, 0.60–2.36 mm),
118 produced from bituminous coal, was used. The carbon was repeatedly washed with hot and cold
119 water and dried at 50 °C for 24 h to obtain pristine GAC.
120 For impregnation, IL was diluted with propan-2-ol (20 mL/g IL), and GAC was added (5 g
121 GAC/g IL). The mixture was stirred for 24 h at 250 rpm, filtered, and dried at 50 °C to obtain
122 impregnated activated carbon (iGAC).

123 The extent of impregnation was calculated as a ratio of the weight increase of iGAC (given
124 as the difference between the weights of iGAC (m_{iGAC}) and GAC (m_{GAC})) and the initial weight
125 of ionic liquid in mixture (m_{IL}):

$$126 \quad [1] \quad w_{IL} = 100 * \frac{m_{iGAC} - m_{GAC}}{m_{IL}}$$

127 Dried iGAC was washed 10 times with an excess of water (250 mL) before the application
128 to eliminate the effect of potential washout of the IL from the AC surface.

129 A leachate of dried iGAC (before washing) was carried out in order to study the leachability
130 of impregnated ILs to water. The weight of 5 g of iGAC was mixed with 50 mL of water and
131 the concentration of leached IL was determined with the aid of UV-VIS spectroscopy. To assess
132 the effectiveness of the impregnation process, the materials were comprehensively
133 characterized using FTIR, SEM/EDS, BET, and UV–VIS analyses. The procedures and results
134 are provided in the supplementary file (chapters S1.1-S1.3; Fig. S1-S4).

135

136 **2.3 Isolation of resistant bacteria from wastewater and detection of ARGs**

137 Resistant bacterial isolates from wastewater were used for antimicrobial activity testing as
138 representatives of environmental bacteria. These isolates were obtained in a previous study [42],
139 which provided a detailed description of their cultivation, identification, and the detection of
140 antibiotic resistance genes.

141 Wastewater sampling was conducted at a WWTP (ÚČOV Ostrava, Czech Republic) in
142 November 2020. The samples were plated on Tryptone Soya Agar (TSA, Sigma-Aldrich)
143 supplemented with ampicillin (Sigma-Aldrich) at a concentration of 500 mg L⁻¹ and incubated
144 at 30 °C for 24 h. Genomic DNA was extracted from the resistant bacterial isolates, and genes
145 conferring resistance to beta-lactams (*bla*TEM, *mecA*), carbapenems (*bla*NDM-1, *bla*KPC,
146 *bla*OXA-48), tetracycline (*tetW*), and vancomycin (*vanA*) were detected using PCR. In this
147 study, ARGs detection was further expanded to include sulfonamide resistance genes (*sul1*),
148 which were not analyzed in the previous publication. All primers and PCR conditions are listed
149 in Supplementary Table S2.

150 Resistant bacterial isolates confirmed to exhibit multidrug resistance were identified via
151 Sanger sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene (SeqMe s.r.o., Dobříš, Czech Republic). The obtained
152 sequences were deposited in the NCBI GenBank under their respective accession numbers.

153 In this study, selected resistant bacterial isolates were subsequently used to evaluate the
154 antimicrobial activity of impregnated activated carbon.

155

156 **2.4 Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry**

157
158 A reliable LC-MS/MS method was developed and validated in our laboratory for the
159 quantification of target analytes in model solutions, grey waters and wastewaters. A gradient
160 liquid chromatograph Nexera X2 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) coupled with a QTRAP 6500+
161 mass spectrometer (AB Sciex, Framingham, MA, USA) was used for the analysis. A detailed
162 description of the method is provided in the Supplementary file (chapter S1.4 and Tab. S3).

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167 2.5 Adsorption tests

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169 The batch adsorption tests with model solutions and real water samples were carried out
170 to examine how the adsorption properties of GAC were affected by the ILs' impregnation. Four
171 pharmaceuticals - paracetamol, ampicillin, ibuprofen, and sulfamethoxazole (all Sigma-
172 Aldrich, MA, USA) - were selected to prepare the model test solutions. The weight of 10 mg
173 of adsorbent (GAC or iGAC) was mixed with 25 mL of demineralized water in a 50 mL
174 Erlenmeyer flask. The volume of 1.5 mL of solution was taken out and filtered to an Eppendorf
175 tube. Then, the volume of 1.5 mL of the pharmaceutical solution (concentration 1 mg L⁻¹) was
176 added to the flask. The procedure was repeated every 24 h. The WWTP influent and effluent
177 (ÚČOV Ostrava, Czech Republic) and greywater (from bathrooms and laundry) from Hotel
178 Zámek Valeč (Czech Republic) were used as real water samples. The weight of 150 mg of the
179 adsorbent was mixed with 5 mL of WWTP sample in a 5 mL Eppendorf tube and the mixture
180 was left at rest for 3 h. Then, the mixture was filtered through cellulose filters (regenerated
181 cellulose membrane filter, 0.45 µm, (Fisherbrand, NH, USA). The greywater samples were
182 treated with the adsorbents in the same way as the WWTP samples.

183 2.6 Antimicrobial activity tests

184 The antimicrobial activity of impregnated activated carbon (iGAC) was evaluated using
185 four approaches: (i) a model solution of *Bacillus subtilis* in water, (ii) resistant *Aeromonas sp.*
186 strains isolated from wastewater, (iii) wastewater from a municipal wastewater treatment plant
187 (WWTP), and (iv) greywater from a hotel.

188 Bacteria were cultivated on Paddle tests (VWR, Czech Republic) with tryptone glucose extract
189 agar containing TTC (2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride) or on 3M Petrifilm Aerobic Count
190 plates (3M, USA). Colony growth was analyzed using ImageJ software.

191 For all tests, 1 g of iGAC was mixed with 1 mL of bacterial suspension or real water sample
192 and kept in contact for 3 h. Subsequently, 200 µL of the mixture was diluted with 800 µL of
193 distilled water and inoculated on the cultivation medium.

194 (i) Model *B. subtilis* solution: Six replicates were tested with *B. subtilis* (Merck, Czech
195 Republic) diluted 1:100. Plates were incubated at 30 °C for 24 h.

196 (ii) Isolated *Aeromonas sp.* strains: Four strains (A1–A4) isolated from WWTP were tested in
197 six replicates with bacterial suspensions diluted 1:1000. Incubation was performed at 28 °C
198 for 24 h.

199 (iii) WWTP wastewater: Samples of WWTP effluent (Ostrava, Czech Republic) were incubated
200 at 28 °C for 48 h.

201 (iv) Greywater: Greywater samples (Hotel Zámek Valeč, Czech Republic) were incubated at
202 28 °C for 24 h under identical conditions.

203

204 **2.6.1 Antimicrobial test evaluation procedure**

205 Bacterial colonies cultivated on agar were analyzed by image analysis using the software
206 ImageJ. ImageJ is an open-source software developed by the National Institutes of Health
207 (NIH), widely used in biology, microbiology, and other scientific fields [43]. Its main functions
208 include both automatic and manual colony counting, measuring their diameter, area, shape, and
209 color intensity. Each sample was photographed together with the scale. The core of the analysis
210 was image conversion to binary (thresholding), which facilitated the detection of individual
211 colonies against a contrasting background. The total area of colonies was recalculated to the
212 scale and expressed in mm². In each experiment, a control sample (bacteria in water without
213 activated carbon) was also placed on the tester, thus eliminating the influence of conditions, and
214 the colony areas were expressed relative to this control in percentage. The evaluation of the
215 antimicrobial tests using ImageJ software is presented in Supplementary in Figure S5.

216

217 **2.7 Ecotoxicity tests**

218 As the iGAC is intended for wastewater treatment, aquatic tests performed with an aqueous
219 leachate prepared from ten times-washed iGAC according to the European standard
220 EN 12457- 4:2002 (liquid to solid ratio 10 L kg⁻¹ dry weight) were selected from the battery of
221 ecotests. A leachate from the pristine (non-impregnated) GAC was also tested using the same
222 methods. The indicator organisms employed were *Vibrio fischeri*, *Sinapis alba*, and *Eisenia*
223 *andrei*, representing bacteria, plant and animal species, respectively.

224 ***Vibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition**

225 The bioluminescence inhibition test was performed following European Standard EN ISO
226 11348-3:2008. Freeze-dried marine bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* NRRL-B-11177 (Hach Lange
227 GmbH, Germany) were reactivated and utilised for luminescence measurements of leachates,
228 with the pH value adjusted to 7 and the salinity modified by the addition of 20 g L⁻¹ NaCl. Light

229 emission of *V. fischeri* after exposure for 15 and 30 min was measured with LUMISTox 300
230 luminometer (Hach Lange GmbH, Germany) at 15 °C in duplicate. Due to the low inhibitory
231 effect of the leachates, bioluminescence was determined only for undiluted leachates and
232 leachates that had been diluted to half of their original concentration.

233 ***Sinapis alba* root growth inhibition**

234 The root growth inhibition test was performed using *Sinapis alba* (mustard) seeds. The
235 test was conducted in 100 mm diameter Petri dishes lined with filter paper, 5 mL of aqueous
236 leachate or dilution water (control), with 20 seeds placed in each dish. The test was conducted
237 within a thermostatically controlled Lovibond ET 619-4 / 140 Liter cabinet (Tintometer GmbH,
238 Germany), maintained at 20 °C in the absence of light for a period of 72 h. The assessment of
239 root length was performed utilizing the ImageJ software [43]. The average root length
240 (determined in triplicates for each sample) was related to the control, and the percentage of root
241 growth inhibition was calculated.

242

243 ***Eisenia andrei* acute toxicity**

244 An acute toxicity test was performed with earthworms *Eisenia andrei* in accordance with
245 OECD guideline No. 207 (1984) for testing of chemicals. In the paper contact toxicity test,
246 individual worms were placed in vials lined with a 64 cm² square of filter paper moistened with
247 1 mL of undiluted aqueous leachate. The vials were then sealed with parafilm and placed in the
248 thermostatically controlled cabinet set at 20 °C without light for 48 h. As the minimum
249 requirement, ten replicates were used for each treatment. After the test, the mortality of the
250 earthworms was assessed based on their response to a gentle mechanical stimulus.

251 **2.8 Data Processing and Statistical Analysis**

252 Data were processed and visualized using OriginPro 2018b software (OriginLab
253 Corporation, USA). Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were applied for
254 statistical evaluation, and the datasets were compared using a t-test or one-way ANOVA at a
255 95% significance level. The number of replicates is specified for each figure, and the statistical
256 evaluation results are indicated using letters (a, b, c) above the boxes in boxplots.

257 3 Results and Discussion

258 3.1 Characterization of impregnated activated carbon

259 The ratio of IL impregnated on the AC surface from the propan-2-ol solution was
260 determined gravimetrically and related to the weight of GAC after drying at 50 °C. Based on
261 the calculated ratios we can state, that TEDA was impregnated to a greater extent than TEGO
262 (Tab. 1). Textural properties of washed GAC and iGACs are shown in Tab.S1. The specific
263 surface as well as the pore volume were reduced more than twice due to the impregnation by
264 both ILs which have indicated the pore plugging during impregnation.

265

266 **Tab. 1** Textural parameters of washed GAC and iGACs and extent of impregnation of ionic
267 liquids TEGO and TEDA

	Specific surface (m² g⁻¹)	Micropore volume (cm³ g⁻¹)	Maximum pore volume (cm³ g⁻¹)	Impregnation extent (wt. %)
GAC	850.06	0.250	0.353	–
iGAC-TEDA	327.20	0.106	0.133	71.51
iGAC-TEGO	380.23	0.068	0.155	85.72

268

269 The FTIR spectra of the original GAC and both impregnated GACs are shown in Fig. 1.
270 The broad band at the 3200-3600 cm⁻¹ region is assigned to OH-stretching vibrations. Small
271 bands between 2800-3000 cm⁻¹ indicate the C-H stretching of alkanes, whereas alkenes are
272 represented by small bands at around 1600 cm⁻¹. Other small bands at around 1400 cm⁻¹ are
273 assigned to the C-H bending of alkanes.

274 Broad band is present at 1000-1200 cm⁻¹, representing aromatic CO groups. [34,44,45]
275 Small bands at around 1100- 1400 cm⁻¹ appeared, corresponding to the S=O stretching of the
276 sulphate or sulfonyl group which are present in TEGO or TEDA (Fig. S1), respectively [44,46].
277 In the case of GAC impregnated with TEDA (iGAC-TEDA), a band appeared at around
278 1100 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of the fluoro group. [34,44,45]

279

280

281 **Fig. 1** FTIR spectra of initial GAC and both impregnated ACs

282 Table 2 represents the results of the SEM/EDS analysis of the initial GAC and
 283 impregnated ACs. It is apparent that the content of sulphur, which is present in both ionic
 284 liquids, has risen on the surfaces of both iGAC-TEGO and iGAC-TEDA. Furthermore,
 285 impregnation of GAC with ionic liquids has led to the increase of the content of fluorine which
 286 is also present in the TEDA structure. Based on the results, supported by the images shown in
 287 Fig. S2, we can conclude that fluorine was somehow present in the TEGO IL as well.

288 **Tab. 2** SEM/EDS analysis of the surfaces of GAC and impregnated activated carbons

Sample	C (at. %)	O (at. %)	S (at. %)	F (at. %)
GAC	96.32	3.36	0.16	0.16
iGAC-TEGO	96.77	2.33	0.53	0.38
iGAC-TEDA	92.84	5.82	0.80	0.56

289 As shown in Fig. S3, it is possible to determinate the TEGO concentration in water with
290 UV-VIS spectroscopy. Based on Tab. 1 and impregnation conditions we assume that the
291 maximum amount of TEGO on the sample lied in hundreds mg. Results presented in Fig. S4
292 indicate that the amount of leached TEGO was negligible (less that 0.5 mg). This means that
293 the maximum ratio of leached TEGO lied in hundredths of % related to the amount of TEGO
294 bonded to the GAC surface.

295 **3.2 Adsorption tests**

296 **3.2.1 Batch adsorption test with model solution**

297 Impregnation of the GAC surface with TEDA had only a negligible impact on the
298 adsorption of most of the contaminants used in this work (Fig. 2). Only in the case of
299 paracetamol removal, a slight deterioration of adsorption capacity was observed (318 mg L^{-1}
300 compared to 482 mg L^{-1} for pristine GAC). A similar effect has occurred in the case of
301 sulfamethoxazole removal; nonetheless, this deterioration was observed only in the case of
302 higher initial concentrations (5.315 mg L^{-1} compared to 5.816 mg L^{-1} for pristine GAC).
303 Impregnation of GAC with TEGO had a similar effect on the adsorption of paracetamol,
304 ibuprofen, and sulfamethoxazole compared to TEDA. Unlike the case of TEDA, impregnation
305 with TEGO lead to a slight reduction of adsorption properties for ampicillin (830 mg L^{-1}
306 compared to 980 mg L^{-1} for pristine GAC). Polymerized ionic liquid, used by Xu and An [39],
307 led to the enhancement of ibuprofen removal from water, whilst the ionic liquid used in this
308 study did not affect the adsorption capacity of GAC significantly. Enhancement of adsorption
309 properties for pharmaceuticals (including ibuprofen, ampicillin, and sulfamethoxazole) due to
310 the impregnation of the adsorbent surface (*Kigelia pinnata* biomass or montmorillonite,
311 respectively) with 1-methyl-3-decahexyl imidazolium ionic liquid was also observed in two
312 studies by Lawal and Moodley [47,48]

313 For the comparison of the adsorption efficiencies between individual pharmaceuticals,
314 it is necessary to recalculate both the adsorbed amount (q) and initial concentration (c_0) to
315 moles. The adsorption capacities on pristine GAC selected for the comparison were
316 $1.46 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ ($220.64 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) at an initial concentration $0.61 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ($91.69 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) for
317 paracetamol, $1.18 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ ($243.52 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) at $0.56 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ($114.89 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for ibuprofen,
318 $1.14 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ ($399.62 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) at $0.55 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ($191.27 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for ampicillin, and
319 $0.59 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ ($148.5 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) at $0.65 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ ($164.27 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for sulfamethoxazole.
320 Paracetamol, ibuprofen, and ampicillin seem to be adsorbed remarkably better than

321 sulfamethoxazole, with paracetamol being slightly better attracted to the GAC surface than the
 322 latter two molecules. The adsorption efficiency can be affected by different factors such as
 323 charge of the molecule (related to its dissociation constant), functional groups, molecular size
 324 and shape, preferred adsorption mechanism, etc. Regarding the dissociation constants, we can
 325 consider that paracetamol is mainly uncharged at neutral pH, ibuprofen is present in an anionic
 326 form, and ampicillin is in a zwitterionic form. On the other hand, sulfamethoxazole has the
 327 highest negative charge due to the deprotonation of sulphonamide nitrogen and a pyridine
 328 nitrogen.

329
 330 **Fig. 2** Adsorption of single contaminants (paracetamol, ibuprofen, ampicillin, and sulfamethoxazole)
 331 from model solutions on pristine GAC and ionic liquid impregnated GACs. Adsorption tests were
 332 performed in three replicates, and the mean values \pm standard deviations are presented.

333 3.2.2 Batch adsorption experiments with WWTP samples

334 Batch adsorption experiments were used to compare individual materials (GAC and
 335 iGAC); therefore, the ratio of the amount of adsorbent and concentration and the volume of the
 336 adsorbate solution were chosen so that the concentrations after adsorption were measurable.
 337 The treatment of WWTP influent with any of the three materials has led to the decrease of the
 338 concentration of more or less all of the 24 micropollutants present in the sample (Fig. 3). The
 339 studied substances were of various nature – pharmaceuticals and their metabolites (metformin,

340 paracetamol, paraxanthine, theophylline, lamotrigine, metoprolol, bisoprolol, telmisartan,
341 irbesartan, losartan, candesartan, diclofenac, furosemide, ibuprofen), stimulants and their
342 metabolites (nicotine, cotinine, caffeine, theobromine), industrial chemicals
343 (1H- benzotriazole, 5,4-methylbenzotriazole), pesticides (DEET), and sweeteners (acesulfame
344 K, saccharin, sucralose). The micropollutants with the highest concentrations were metformin,
345 sucralose, caffeine, and 1H-benzotriazole with the initial concentrations over $40 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.
346 The removal efficiency surpassed 50 % only for five studied contaminants: lamotrigine (84 %),
347 bisoprolol (61 %), DEET (59 %), 1H-benzotriazole (58 %), and metoprolol (51 %).
348 The adsorption of the studied pollutants was not significantly improved after the modification
349 of the GAC surface with ILs. In the case of the modification with TEGO the adsorption was
350 even decreased for 18 from 24 of the studied pollutants. The highest uptake improvement was
351 observed in the case of ibuprofen (45 % compared to 23 % for pristine GAC). Unlike in the
352 previous case, the surface modification with TEDA ionic liquid led to the slight enhancement
353 of the adsorption of most analysed contaminants. The most distinct improvements were
354 observed in the case of saccharin (74 % compared to 43 % for pristine GAC), ibuprofen (53 %
355 compared to 23 % for GAC), and caffeine (58 % compared to 37 % for pristine GAC).

356 In the case of WWTP effluent treatment (Fig. 3), only metformin and sucralose were present
357 in significant amounts in the effluent; both of them were present in concentration levels higher
358 than $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while the rest of the contaminants were reduced under $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ during
359 wastewater treatment. The removal efficiency >50 % was observed only in the case of DEET
360 (60 %) and losartan (59 %). The most distinct removal improvement was observed in the case
361 of caffeine which went from negligible sorption to 60 % removal for iGAC-TEGO and 87 %
362 for iGAC-TEDA, respectively. Impregnation of the GAC with TEDA led to the enhancement
363 of the adsorption of multiple contaminants, such as lamotrigine (from 36 % to 71 %),
364 furosemide (from 23 % to 54 %), losartan (from 59 % to 88 %), 1H-benzotriazole (from 49 %
365 to 70 %), or metoprolol (from 36 % to 56 %). Ruhl et al., 2014 [49] used nine samples of
366 powder activated carbon for the treatment of WWTP effluent, containing, among other
367 diclofenac, metoprolol, 1H-benzotriazole, methyl benzotriazole, and acesulfame K. The initial
368 concentration of diclofenac ($2.8 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was very close to our work ($2.6 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), and the
369 adsorption removals were in the range of 34-64 %. GAC used in our work removed 30 %, iGAC
370 prepared with the use of TEGO and TEDA had removal efficiency of 25 and 32 %, respectively.
371 For the other four contaminants, the initial concentrations were noticeably higher than in our
372 work. The removal efficiencies were 42.9-89 % for 1H-benzotriazole (49-70 % in our work),

373 76-90 % for methyl benzotriazole (43-60 % in our work), and above 90 % for metoprolol (26-
374 56 % in our work).

375 The impregnation of the GAC surface with ILs may have affected the possible adsorption
376 mechanisms in several ways; lowered porosity and specific surface most likely led to the
377 inhibition of the pore filling mechanism. On the other hand, both ILs are hydrophobic;
378 therefore, we can consider that impregnation of GAC with ILs enhanced the hydrophobic
379 interactions adsorption mechanism. Furthermore, impregnation with ILs affected the surface
380 chemistry and most likely the surface charge of the GAC, which could have an impact on
381 electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bond adsorption mechanisms as well. The presence of
382 another species in the real wastewater sample (including inorganic ions or diffused organic
383 matter) also played an important role in affecting the adsorption process. All above mentioned
384 aspects could explain why impregnation with TEDA leads to the general improvement of the
385 removal of the studied contaminants, whilst the impregnation of TEGO had a rather opposite
386 effect. It is important to consider the possible presence of various additives in TEGO IL, being
387 a commercial product.

388
389 **Fig. 3** WWTP influent (A) and effluent (B) treatment via adsorption on pristine GAC and ionic liquid
390 impregnated GACs. The original wastewater sample is designated as the control. Insert in part A
391 shows the total concentration of all micropollutants in the WWTP influent before (control) and after

392 (GAC, iGAC-TEGO, iGAC-TEDA) treatment. Adsorption tests were performed in three replicates,
393 and the mean values \pm standard deviations are presented.

394 *A-Metformin, B-Nicotine, C-Cotinine, D-Theobromine, E-Paracetamol, F-Paraxanthine, G-Theophylline, H-
395 Lamotrigine, I-Metoprolol, J-Caffeine, K-Bisoprolol, L-1H-Benzotriazole, M-Telmisartan, N-5/4 – Methyl-
396 Benzotriazole, O-DEET, P-Irbesartan, Q-Losartan, R-Candesartan, S-Diclofenac, T-Furosemide, U-Ibuprofen, V-
397 Acesulfame K, W-Saccharin, X-Sucralose

398 **3.2.3 Batch adsorption experiments with greywater samples**

399 In comparison with the WWTP samples, a reduced number of pollutants was selected
400 to be examined in greywater samples – metformin, nicotine, theobromine, paracetamol,
401 paraxanthine, theophylline, metoprolol, caffeine, 1H-benzotriazole, and DEET (Fig. 4).
402 Metformin and caffeine were the most represented contaminants in greywater samples with the
403 concentration range of 25-35 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The rest of the contaminants were present in
404 concentrations lower than 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The adsorption efficiencies on GAC were generally lower
405 than 50 %. The removal of micropollutants from greywater was not significantly improved by
406 the impregnation of activated carbon. In the case of iGACs, a slight improvement in adsorption
407 capacity was observed for paraxanthine and 1H-benzotriazole. Another slight improvement
408 occurred in the case of the adsorption of theobromine and theophylline on AC impregnated with
409 TEDA. Hernández-Leal et al., 2011 [50] reached 93% removal of caffeine from greywater in a
410 GAC column operated at low flow. Abd-ur-Rehman et al., 2022 [51] studied the removal of
411 various common contaminants, including paracetamol and DEET, from synthetic greywater
412 with the aid of various adsorbents. The removal efficiency on carbonaceous adsorbents was
413 <20 % for paracetamol and approx. 10-60 % for DEET, the initial concentration of both
414 substances was 5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

415

416 **Fig. 4** Greywater with the use of initial GAC and impregnated GACs. The original greywater sample
 417 is designated as the control. Adsorption tests were performed in three replicates, and the mean
 418 values \pm standard deviations are presented.

419 *A-Metformin, B-Nicotine, D-Theobromine, E-Paracetamol, F-Paraxanthine, G-Theophylline, I-Metoprolol,
 420 J- Caffeine, L- 1H-Benzotriazole, O-DEET

421

422 3.3 Characterization of resistant bacteria from wastewater

423 Four resistant bacterial strains (designated A1–A4) isolated from wastewater at a
 424 WWTP were selected to study the antimicrobial activity of impregnated activated carbon
 425 (iGAC). All bacterial isolates were identified as *Aeromonas* sp. through 16S rRNA sequencing.
 426 The corresponding NCBI accession numbers are listed in Table 3.

427 *Aeromonas* sp. is a gram-negative bacterium commonly found in aquatic environments.
 428 It plays a critical role in the One Health concept, as it has been increasingly associated with the
 429 dissemination of ARGs in recent years, posing a significant public health concern [52–54].

430 The presence of ARGs *bla*TEM, *bla*NDM-1, *tet*W, and *sul*1 was confirmed in these
 431 bacterial isolates (Table 3). The individual bacterial isolates carried the following resistances:
 432 A1 - resistant to beta-lactams and tetracyclines, A2 - resistant to beta-lactams, tetracyclines and
 433 sulphonamides, A3 - resistant to beta-lactams, carbapenems, tetracyclines and sulphonamides,
 434 A4 - resistant to beta-lactams, tetracyclines and sulphonamides.

435 All isolates were tested positive for the *bla*TEM gene, one of the most widespread ARGs
 436 in the environment, often considered as an indicator of anthropogenic antibiotic resistance
 437 contamination [55]. The *sul1* gene, commonly detected in WWTP effluents, is a key component
 438 of class 1 integrons and serves as an indicator of bacterial potential for horizontal gene transfer
 439 [56]. The *tetW* gene, associated with tetracycline resistance, is widely prevalent due to the
 440 extensive use of tetracyclines in veterinary medicine, making it a marker of veterinary antibiotic
 441 contamination [57]. Carbapenems are last-resort antibiotics, and the presence and spread of
 442 *bla*NDM-1 in the environment represent a serious threat to the effective treatment of bacterial
 443 infections [58].

444 **Tab. 3** Detection of ARGs in isolated bacterial strains from wastewater. Accession numbers of
 445 individual isolates come from the NCBI GeneBank database. The *bla*TEM gene encodes a TEM-type β -
 446 lactamase conferring resistance to penicillins and cephalosporins, the *bla*NDM-1 gene encodes the New
 447 Delhi metallo- β -lactamase responsible for carbapenem resistance, the *tetW* gene encodes a ribosomal
 448 protection protein conferring resistance to tetracyclines, and the *sul1* gene encodes a resistant variant of
 449 dihydropteroate synthase responsible for sulfonamide resistance.

Isolate	<i>bla</i> TEM	<i>bla</i> NDM-1	<i>tetW</i>	<i>sul1</i>	Accession Number
A1	+		+		OL832099
A2	+		+	+	OL832103
A3	+	+	+	+	OL832106
A4	+		+	+	OL832108

450 3.4 Antibacterial activity of impregnated activated carbon

451 3.4.1 *Bacillus subtilis* – model organism

452 Tests were performed on the model organism *Bacillus subtilis*. The results confirmed
 453 the high efficacy of granular activated carbon impregnation with ionic liquids TEDA and
 454 TEGO against *Bacillus subtilis*. The average colony size for untreated GAC was 21.7%, for
 455 iGAC-TEDA 13.4%, and for iGAC-TEGO 21.2%, with the control set at 100%. Statistically
 456 significant differences were observed between the control and all tested groups (GAC, iGAC-
 457 TEDA, iGAC-TEGO), as well as between most tested pairs, except the GAC–iGAC-TEGO
 458 pair, where no significant difference was detected. This suggests that the use of ionic liquids,
 459 particularly TEDA, enhances the antimicrobial effectiveness of GAC.

460
 461 **Fig. 5** Results of *Bacillus subtilis* antimicrobial tests. The mean value of the control sample area was
 462 set to 100 %. The tests were performed in six replicates. A one-way ANOVA was used for the statistical
 463 evaluation at a 95% significance level. Different letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant
 464 differences between the datasets.

465

466 3.4.2 *Aeromonas* sp. isolated from WWTP

467 Antimicrobial activity of iGAC was statistically more successful against *Aeromonas* sp.
 468 with antibiotic resistance genes (bacterial strains labelled A1-A4), see Fig. 6. Although
 469 impregnation did not lead to a statistically significant improvement in the A1 strain, there was
 470 a statistically significant improvement in the A2 strain for iGAC-TEGO, and in the A3 and A4
 471 strains for both impregnated materials, with >99% elimination of bacteria.

472 These results were achieved at a significance level $p < 0.05$ (t-test), confirming the high
 473 efficacy of granular activated carbon impregnation with ionic liquids TEDA and TEGO against
 474 bacteria carrying antibiotic resistance genes.

475 For strain A1, the average relative colony size for GAC impregnated with TEDA was
 476 15.52% and 17.35%, while the control value was 100% - however, these differences were not

477 statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level (t-test). For strain A2, the relative colony
 478 size of iGAC-TEGO decreased to 2.31%, representing a statistically significant decrease
 479 compared to the control (100%) and pristine GAC (65%). The most pronounced effect was
 480 observed for strains A3 and A4, where the relative colony size after impregnation with both
 481 ionic liquids decreased almost to zero. The relative colony size of A3 for iGAC-TEDA was
 482 0.13% and iGAC-TEGO 0.06%, which represents statistically significant results, both against
 483 the control (100%) and pure GAC (69%). For the A4 gene, the relative colony size of iGAC-
 484 TEDA was 0% and iGAC-TEGO 0.87%, which confirms the high efficiency of this method in
 485 eliminating bacteria with antibiotic resistance genes.

486 **Fig. 6** Results of ARGs antimicrobial tests. The mean value of the control sample area was set to
 487 100 %. **A1** - resistant to beta-lactams and tetracyclines, **A2** - resistant to beta-lactams, tetracyclines
 488 and sulfonamides, **A3** - resistant to beta-lactams, carbapenems, tetracyclines and sulfonamides, **A4** -
 489 resistant to beta-lactams, tetracyclines and sulfonamides. The tests were performed in six replicates. A
 490 one-way ANOVA was used for the statistical evaluation at a 95% significance level. Different letters
 491 (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences between the datasets.

492
 493
 494

495 **3.4.3 Wastewater and greywater samples**

496 For real wastewater samples (Fig. 7), both ILs contributed to the inhibition of bacterial
497 growth compared to the control and GAC.

498 In the real water sample, the relative colony area for iGAC-TEDA decreased to 17.82%
499 and for iGAC-TEGO to 17.98% compared to the control (100 %). For iGAC-TEDA, there was
500 a statistically significant decrease also compared to GAC (49%). For the grey water sample, a
501 statistically significant inhibition at the 0.05 significance level was recorded for both
502 impregnated materials iGAC-TEDA (44%) and iGAC-TEGO (57%) compared to the control
503 (100%) and also for iGAC-TEDA compared to GAC (75%).

504

505 **Fig. 7** Antimicrobial test of A – wastewater (WWTP Ostrava, effluent) and B – greywater samples.

506 The mean value of the control sample area was set to 100 %. The tests were performed in six
507 replicates. A one-way ANOVA was used for the statistical evaluation at a 95% significance level.

508 Different letters (a, b, c) indicate statistically significant differences between the datasets.

509 Our results demonstrate the potential of granular activated carbon impregnated with
510 ionic liquids to inhibit bacterial growth in various waters, including ARG strains isolated from
511 WWTP. In the model organism *Bacillus subtilis*, no statistically significant improvement in
512 antimicrobial activity was observed compared to non-impregnated GAC. It has been published
513 several times, that ILs can exhibit antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis*, with efficacy
514 influenced by factors such as alkyl chain length, cation type, and anion composition [59–61].
515 However, direct studies on the antimicrobial effects of immobilized ILs on *B. subtilis* are
516 limited.

517 In contrast, a notable antimicrobial effect was observed in *Aeromonas* strains isolated
518 from WWTP. In some cases, GAC impregnation with ILs led to more than 99% reduction in
519 bacterial viability. It is therefore obvious that ionic liquids can have different effects on different
520 microorganisms, as has been previously documented in the literature [62,63].

521 Similar effects were observed in real wastewater and greywater samples. It was shown
522 that the significant inhibition of bacterial growth of GAC impregnated with TEDA and TEGO
523 occurred not only under laboratory conditions but also in complex matrices. While ILs have
524 strong potential as antimicrobial agents, as shown in sludge-based tests [64–66], their use for
525 direct bacterial suppression in actual wastewater treatment processes is rare [67].

526 Compared to other advanced oxidation or membrane-based methods, adsorption offers
527 advantages such as lower energy requirements and potential reusability of the material [68]. On
528 the other hand, although ILs offer promising results, there are challenges related to their
529 toxicity, biodegradability, and economic feasibility that need to be addressed for their broader
530 practical application [69]. Therefore, further long-term testing under real operational conditions
531 is required, along with an evaluation of the environmental impact of ionic liquid use.

532 **3.5 Ecotoxicity of ionic liquids, granulated activated carbon and impregnated activated** 533 **carbon**

534 Ionic liquids are frequently classified as environmentally friendly green solvents.
535 Nevertheless, when (eco)toxicity is the focal point, numerous ionic liquids pose an
536 environmental threat [70]. The commercially available IL TEGO Dispers 662 C used in this
537 study is considered a water pollutant based on the information provided in the product safety
538 data sheet. It is not allowed to enter soil, waterways or wastewater canal. This assertion is
539 supported with ecotoxicity data, ranging from EC50 0.065 mg L⁻¹ for *Daphnia magna* to
540 EC50 564 mg L⁻¹ for activated sludge bacteria (see Supplementary material, Tab. S4). For the
541 IL TEDA, EC50 of 0.51 and 0.45 mg L⁻¹ was observed for *Vibrio fischeri* luminescence
542 inhibition after 15- and 30-min incubation, respectively [22] Concerning these values, TEDA
543 can be classified as highly toxic, according to the already used hazard ranking by Passino and
544 Smith [71]

545 The findings of our study demonstrate that the aforementioned toxic ILs have the potential
546 to bind firmly to the surface of GAC, thereby negating their environmental hazard, despite the
547 fact the ILs are present in iGAC in high concentrations (up to 17 wt.%). The results of the

548 ecotoxicity tests (see Tab. 4) confirmed that the aqueous leachate from iGAC did not exert a
 549 significant ecotoxic effect on any of the indicator organisms. *V. fischeri* bioluminescence was
 550 only slightly inhibited for iGAC-TEGO leachate, with the inhibition value not exceeding 10%
 551 after 30 min incubation. Raw data on luminescence intensity can be found in Table S5. *S. alba*
 552 root growth was slightly inhibited in case of the iGAC-TEDA leachate (12.10% inhibition
 553 compared to control). Conversely, a slight growth stimulation was observed for the iGAC-
 554 TEGO leachate. Considering the values of standard deviations, it can be stated that the average
 555 root length is comparable to the control determination for all samples (see Fig. 8). Acute toxicity
 556 test conducted with earthworms *E. andrei* exhibited no mortality in any of the determinations.

557 Given the negligible inhibitory (and zero mortality) effects, no ecotoxicity assessment of
 558 the dilution series was conducted. Consequently, no median effective nor lethal concentration
 559 (EC50, LC50) could be ascertained for any of the indicator organisms employed. The ILs were
 560 likely to be firmly attached to the surface of the AC, which resulted in the aqueous leachate
 561 from the ten-times-washed iGAC being considered non-toxic.

562 **Tab. 4** Results of ecotoxicity tests conducted with indicator organisms *V. fischeri*, *S. alba*, *E. andrei*.
 563 (mean value \pm standard deviation; 2 replicates for *V. fischeri*, 3 replicates (3x20 seeds) for *S. alba*, 10
 564 replicates for *E. andrei*) Negative values indicate stimulation of the monitored parameters
 565 (luminescence, root growth).

Sample	<i>V. fischeri</i> luminescence inhibition (%)		<i>S. alba</i> root growth inhibition (%)	<i>E. andrei</i> mortality (%)
	15 min	30 min		
GAC	1.60 \pm 6.09	1.70 \pm 4.42	-3.79 \pm 5.09	0
iGAC-TEGO	14.41 \pm 1.24	9.81 \pm 0.82	-10.71 \pm 9.14	0
iGAC-TEDA	8.73 \pm 0.83	1.01 \pm 0.05	12.10 \pm 6.42	0

566

567 **Fig. 8** Root length of *S. alba* after 72 h of germination, each treatment was performed in
 568 triplicate

569 **4 Conclusions**

570 Commercial granular activated carbon was impregnated with two ionic liquids (ILs),
 571 TEGO® Dispers 662C and N,N,N-triethyl-1-dodecylammonium bis(trifluoromethyl-
 572 sulfonyl)imide (TEDA). TEGO was selected as a representative of cost-effective ILs, while
 573 TEDA represented a group of quaternary ammonium ionic liquids known for their biocidal
 574 properties. The impregnation of GAC by ILs did not significantly decrease its sorption
 575 efficiency for micropollutants in wastewater from WWTP and greywater. Both ionic liquids
 576 showed a statistically significant improvement in effective inhibition of viable strains of
 577 *Aeromonas* sp. carrying ARGs, which had been isolated from the wastewater of WWTP. In
 578 conclusion, the attachment of ionic liquids to a suitable carrier represents a promising strategy
 579 to limit the environmental spread of antibiotic resistance.

580

581

582 **Acknowledgements**

583 The authors thank Kamil Maciej Górecki for performing FTIR analyses, Jana Strakošová for
584 performing Elemental analyses and Jaroslav Lang for his support and assistance during the
585 experiments.

586 **Author contributions: CRediT**

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595 Supervision, Investigation.

596 **Funding**

597 The work was supported by the OP JAK project “INOVO!!!”, No.
598 CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008588 supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
599 and co-financed by the European Union. This work was financially supported by the European
600 Union under the REFRESH Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech
601 Industries project No. CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just
602 Transition. Experimental results were accomplished by using Large Research Infrastructure
603 ENREGAT supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic
604 under project No. LM2023056.

605

606 Data is available online via the ZENODO repository.

607 A preprint has been submitted to Research Square. Title: Modification of activated carbon using
608 ionic liquids for concurrent elimination of micropollutants and antibiotic-resistant bacteria from
609 wastewater. RSID: rs-8206670.

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